

EUROPEAN
INTERNATIONAL
UNIVERSITY

COVER PAGE AND DECLARATION

	Master of Science (MS) in IT & Data Science
Specialisation:	
Module Code & Module Title:	MSITDS520 Big Data Technologies and Analytics
Students' Full Name:	Mony Ho
Word Count:	3304
Date of Submission:	25 August 2024

I confirm that this assignment is my own work, is not copied from any other person's work (published/unpublished), and has not been previously submitted for assessment elsewhere.

E-SIGNATURE:

DATE:

25 August 2024

EIU Paris City Campus

Address: 59 Rue Lamarck, 75018 Paris, France | **Tel:** +33188320435 | **Mobile/WhatsApp:** +33607591197 | **Email:** paris@eiu.ac

EIU Operations HQ

Address: 16th Fl. Amarin Tower, 496-502, Room No.2.1 Ploenchit Rd., Bangkok 10330, Thailand | **Tel:** +66(2)256923 & +66(2)2569908 | **Mobile/WhatsApp:** +33607591197 | **Email:** info@eiu.ac

Table of Content

Introduction-----	1
Main Body -----	1
Data Ingestion and Pre-processing-----	2
Big Data Technologies-----	6
Data Analytics -----	9
Data Visualization-----	15
Conclusion -----	19
References -----	20

Introduction

According to BasuMallick (2022), “Big data is a quantity of data that is enormous in volume and is constantly expanding rapidly. No typical data management systems can effectively store or analyze this data because of its magnitude and complexity. Big data is a collection of organized, semi-structured, and unstructured information gathered by businesses that can be mined for information and utilized in advanced applications of analytics like predictive modeling and machine learning. Together with technologies that support big data analytics purposes, systems that process and store big data have become a regular part of business data management infrastructures.” There are many advantages of big data integration into a business or organization include: cost reduction, product development, strategic business decisions, customer experience, risk management, entertainment, education, health care, government, marketing, and banking (Staff, 2024).

Objective of this report is working on analysis a large dataset using big data technologies and analytics techniques and summarizing the findings. The main points of analysis criteria include data ingestion and pre-processing, big data technologies, data analytics and data visualization. For the real-world dataset, this report uses an actual business dataset of a microfinance institution namely, PTC Microfinance Plc. is located at Kampot province, Cambodia. The dataset stores the loan information of customers such as ‘Customer ID’, ‘Surname’, ‘Given Name’, ‘Loan Account Number’, ‘Sanctioned Loan Amount’, ‘Currency’, ‘Disbused Loan Amount’, ‘Loan Status’, ‘Risk in Percentage’, ‘Location’, and ‘Reason For Taking Loan’. And the dataset is store in MySQL database online and it will be used to analyze with Apache Hadoop, an open source Java-based software platform that manages data processing and storage for big data applications (*Apache Hadoop: What Is It and How Can You Use It?*, n.d.). Microsoft Power BI is also used by importing data from Apache Hadoop to visualize and summarize the data on dashboard.

Main Body

The dataset is used to analyze the risk of loan of PTC Microfinance Plc. by working with contain complete details of all loan issued, including the current loan status (current, late, fully paid, etc.) and latest payment information. The finding of the analysis will solve the problems related to overall average risks calculation, average risk per location calculation, average risk per category

and loan type calculation, and average risk per location and category calculation. The overall technologies, tools and operating systems are used in this project including Apache Hadoop, Apache Sqoop, Apache Pig, HDFS Architecture work in Ubuntu Linux OS and Power BI works in Windows 10 OS. The project's scenario, first is importing dataset from the database of the company by using Apache Sqoop, second is cleaning and preparing data by using Apache Pig, third is analyze data by using Apache Pig, and forth is visualizing data by import data from Hadoop File System to Power BI to visualize and summarize data.

Before working on data ingestion, Ubuntu Linux OS need to be tested to make sure it connects to the internet, Apache Hadoop and its services are running by using the following commands.

```
sudo ping -c 4 google.com
```

```
./start-all.sh
```

```
jps
```



```
root@hadoop:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin# jps
6648 ResourceManager
7081 Jps
6314 DataNode
6507 SecondaryNameNode
6123 NameNode
6767 NodeManager
root@hadoop:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin#
```

Figure 1. Using 'jps' command to displays Hadoop running services

Data Ingestion and Pre-processing

Effectiveness of data ingestion and pre-processing techniques used

Apache Sqoop is one of another effectiveness of data ingestion and pre-processing techniques used to ingest dataset from other database server. It very handful to connect the dataset from the SQL Queries into Hadoop distributed file system (GeeksforGeeks, 2021). To allow Sqoop can connect and import data from a database server, it need some information including server name,

database name, database username, database user password, and database port number. So, to connect to the company's database Sqoop need the database information as describe below.

Server: sql12.freemysqlhosting.net

Name: sql12723594

Username: sql12723594

Password: DgNdw8ceG9

Port number: 3306

Figure 2. Database of company in MySQL database

Command below is used to check the information in Hadoop file system and the result there is nothing except 'tmp' folder.

hadoop fs -ls /

```
Found 1 items
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup          0 2024-08-01 15:39 /tmp
root@hadoop: /usr/local/hadoop/sbin#
```

Figure 3. The information in Hadoop file system

The command lines below are used to connect and import dataset from the company's database by using Sqoop syntax follow by the provided database information. The imported data is stored in a new directory called 'sqoop_out'.

```
sqoop import --connect jdbc:mysql://sql12.freemysqlhosting.net/sql12723594 --username sql12723594 --password DgNdw8ceG9 --table Customers --target-dir /sqoop_out
```

```
root@hadoop:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin# sqoop import --connect jdbc:mysql://sql12.freemysqlhosting.net/sql12723594 --username sql12723594 --password DgNdw8ceG9 --table Customers --target-dir /sqoop_out
```

Figure 4. Using 'sqoop' commands to import database's company to Hadoop file system

After completed, the retrieved number of records in the dataset is displayed, in this case the result is 'Retrieved 101 records'.

```
24/08/03 13:34:19 INFO mapreduce.ImportJobBase: Transferred 7.3506 KB i
24/08/03 13:34:19 INFO mapreduce.ImportJobBase: Retrieved 101 records.
```

Figure 5. Number of records retrieved from table of database

As stated by (*How Sqoop Internally Works*, 2018), "Sqoop is running a map-only job which each mapper running a query with a specific range to prevent any kind of overlap. The mapper then just drops the data in the target-dir HDFS directory with a file named part-m-00000 (well, the 2nd on ends with 00001 and the 3rd one ends with 00002). The composite export is represented by the target-dir HDFS directory (basically follows the MapReduce naming scheme of files)." The 'hadoop fs -ls /sqoop_out' command line is used to list all file named after importing.

```
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 0 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/_SUCCESS
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 1884 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/part-m-00000
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 1855 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/part-m-00001
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 1843 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/part-m-00002
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 1945 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/part-m-00003
```

Figure 6. Data stores in 'sqoop_out' directory after imported

To validate the imported data, the following command lines are used to list contain in 'sqoop_out' directory and display all data in '/sqoop_out/part-m-000*' file.

```
hadoop fs -cat /sqoop_out/part-m-0000*
```

The result is displaying all the data of imported dataset in part-m-00000, part-m-00001, part-m-00002, part-m-00003.

```
root@hadoop:/usr/local/hadoop/sbin# hadoop fs -cat /sqoop_out/part-m-000*
24/08/03 13:54:20 WARN util.NativeCodeLoader: Unable to load native-hadoop library for your platform
va classes where applicable
0,Surname,Given Name,Loan Account Number,0,Currency,0,Loan Status,0,Location,Reason For Taking Loan
1,ANG,MALIS,HHLNOI240101,30000,USD,25000,Current,20,Prey Veng,Mortgage
2,BOL,VIRUT ,HPLNOD240101,15000,USD,13000,Late,10,Takeo,Small business loan
3,BON,VIROT ,HVL0U240101,7000,USD,5000,Current,7,Koh Kong,Auto loan
4,BUNTHOEUN,VICHETH,HRLOF240101,2000,USD,2000,Closed,0,Kep,Personal loan
5,CHAN,VEASNA,HHLNOI240102,30000,USD,25000,Current,20,Phnom Penh,Mortgage
6,CHHAY,VANNOY ,HPLNOD240102,15000,USD,13000,Late,10,Svay Rieng,Small business loan
7,CHHEANG,VANNET ,HVL0U240102,7000,USD,5000,Current,7,Kandal,Auto loan
8,CHHEL,VANNARA,HRLOF240102,2000,USD,2000,Closed,0,Prey Veng,Personal loan
```

Figure 7. Displaying the data content

Data cleaning and preparation

There are many tools to clean and prepare data before analysis and Apache Pig is one the many tools that is easy to use in cleaning and preparing data. Pig commands can be used in ‘grunt’ shell prompt. In this case, Pig will remove ‘CustomerID’ number 0 because it is the column header and will remove some rows that have null value in ‘Currency’ column. The first step is ‘s1’ variable store data from loading all parts from ‘sqoop_out’ directory and prepare all columns to store.

```
s1 = load '/sqoop_out/part-m-000*' using PigStorage(',') as (CustomerID:int,
Surname:chararray, GivenName:chararray, LoanAccountNumber:chararray,
SanctionedLoanAmount:float, Currency:chararray, DisbusedLoanAmount:float,
LoanStatus:chararray, RiskInPercentage:float, Location:chararray,
ReasonForTakingLoan:chararray);
```

```
grunt> s1 = load '/sqoop_out/part-m-000*' using PigStorage(',') as (CustomerID:int,Surname:chararray,GivenName:chararray
,LoanAccountNumber:chararray,SanctionedLoanAmount:float,Currency:chararray,DisbusedLoanAmount:float,LoanStatus:chararray
,RiskInPercentage:float,location:chararray,ReasonForTakingLoan:chararray);
2024-08-03 15:44:18,036 [main] INFO org.apache.hadoop.conf.Configuration.deprecation - fs.default.name is deprecated. I
nstead, use fs.defaultFS
```

Figure 8. Loading data to PigStorage

The second step is 's2' variable stores the data of some rows without 'null' value in 'Currency' column. And 'filteredData' variable is store all rows of 's2' variable except 'CustomerID' row number 0.

The third step is 'filteredData' variable is stored in '/sqoop_out/filteredData.csv'.

```
grunt> s2 = filter s1 by Currency!='null';
grunt> filteredData = filter s2 by CustomerID >0;
grunt> store filteredData into '/sqoop_out/filteredData.csv' using PigStorage(',');
2024-08-03 16:12:32,382 [main] INFO org.apache.hadoop.conf.Configuration.deprecatio
instead, use fs.defaultFS
```

Figure 9. Filtering data in Pig

The 'dump' command can be used to see the data after cleaning.

```
grunt> dump filteredData;
2024-08-03 15:50:13,740 [main] INFO org.apache.pig.tools.pigstats.ScriptSta
2024-08-03 15:50:13,786 [main] INFO org.apache.hadoop.conf.Configuration.de
```

Figure 10. Display data in Pig

All the steps can be validated again by listing the Hadoop file system information.

```
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 0 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/_SUCCESS
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup 0 2024-08-03 16:12 /sqoop_out/filteredData.csv
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 1884 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/part-m-00000
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 1855 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/part-m-00001
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 1843 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/part-m-00002
-rw-r--r-- 1 root supergroup 1945 2024-08-03 13:34 /sqoop_out/part-m-00003
```

Figure 11. Listing the Hadoop file system information

Big Data Technologies

Selection of appropriate technologies

According to (*What Is Hadoop: Architecture, Modules, Advantages, History - Javatpoint*, n.d.), "Hadoop is an open source framework from Apache and is used to store process and analyze data which are very huge in volume. Hadoop is written in Java and is not OLAP (online analytical

processing). It is used for batch/offline processing. It is being used by Facebook, Yahoo, Google, Twitter, LinkedIn and many more. Moreover, it can be scaled up just by adding nodes in the cluster.” There are many Hadoop distributions such as Apache, Cloudera, HortonWorks, MapR, Intel, Pivota HD, etc., ... In this project Apache Hadoop is used on Ubuntu Linux OS for the big data analytics.

Effective configuration and management

Figure 12. Hadoop management interface on web browser

Apache Hadoop provides two ways of configuration and management tasks. It allows by using commands or web browser. Here are some important Hadoop commands that frequently have been used. ‘./start-all.sh’ is used to start services of Hadoop. ‘./stop-all.sh’ is used to stop services of Hadoop. ‘jps’ is used to check all Hadoop daemons, including NameNode, DataNode, NodeManager, and ResourceManager that are running on server (*What Is the Purpose of the JPS Command in Hadoop ? | ResearchGate*, n.d.). The ‘hadoop fs -ls /’ is used to list Hadoop file system location information. The ‘hadoop fs -put ’ is used to upload file from local location to Hadoop file system location. The ‘hadoop fs -get ’ is used to download file from Hadoop file system location to local location. The ‘hadoop fs -cat ’ is used to read file from Hadoop file system. Apache Hadoop also provides browser interface for management. Here is the UI that can be opened in a web browser by going to localhost with port 8088. It displays

nodes and the memory amount has been specified minimum and the maximum. And it also can be used this to get all the details username and program used. It displays the node ID on which node it is running for example node label. In log menu link if any error occurs, they can be browsed these logs and find the issue.

On a browser with another Tab, type local host with the port number (localhost:50070) to access information on the Clusters. On Local Host shows the basically the distributed file systems Health and it has a number of tabs that can be used for management.

Figure 13. Cluster information management interface on web browser.

Here, it allows administrators to browse the file system in the browser instead of using the console. So, the administrators can see Hadoop directories here as well.

Figure 14. Hadoop directories management interface on web browser

Use of distributed systems and parallel processing

Ranadive (2024) stated that “HDFS is a distributed file system for storing very large data files, running on clusters of commodity hardware. It is fault tolerant, scalable, and extremely simple to expand. Hadoop comes bundled with HDFS (Hadoop Distributed File Systems). When data exceeds the capacity of storage on a single physical machine, it becomes essential to divide it across a number of separate machines. A file system that manages storage specific operations across a network of machines is called a distributed file system. HDFS is one such software.” So HDFS plays as important role in Hadoop for distributed systems and parallel processing.

Data Analytics

Selection of appropriate methods

Pig is also one the best tools for using to analyze data in Hadoop. And it can read imported data from Sqoop directly. The first analysis solves the problems related to overall average risks calculation.

```
s1 = load '/sqoop_out/filteredData.csv' using PigStorage(',') as (CustomerID:int,
Surname:chararray, GivenName:chararray, LoanAccountNumber:chararray,
SanctionedLoanAmount:float, Currency:chararray, DisbusedLoanAmount:float,
LoanStatus:chararray, RiskInPercentage:float, Location:chararray,
ReasonForTakingLoan:chararray);

describe s1;

s2 = group s1 all;

describe s2;

s3 = foreach s2 generate AVG(s1.RiskInPercentage);

dump s3;
```



```
grunt> s3 = foreach s2 gener
grunt> dump s3;
(10.216494845360824)
grunt>
```

Figure 15. Result of the first analysis

The second analysis solves the problems related to overall average risk per location calculation.

```
r1 = load '/sqoop_out/filteredData.csv' using PigStorage(',') as (CustomerID:int,
Surname:chararray, GivenName:chararray, LoanAccountNumber:chararray,
SanctionedLoanAmount:float, Currency:chararray, DisbusedLoanAmount:float,
LoanStatus:chararray, RiskInPercentage:float, Location:chararray,
ReasonForTakingLoan:chararray);

r2 = group r1 by Location;

r3 = foreach r2 generate group,AVG(r1.RiskInPercentage);
```

```
dump r3;
```

```
store r3 into '/AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerLocation';
```

```
(Kep,10.1666666666666666)
(Takeo,10.5333333333333333)
(Kandal,9.928571428571429)
(Koh Kong,10.428571428571429)
(Prey Veng,9.428571428571429)
(Phnom Penh,10.142857142857142)
(Svay Rieng,10.857142857142858)
grunt>
grunt> store r3 into '/AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerLocation';
```

Figure 16. Result of the second analysis

The third analysis solves the problems related to overall average risk per category and loan type calculation.

```
c1 = load '/sqoop_out/filteredData.csv' using PigStorage(',') as (CustomerID:int,
Surname:chararray, GivenName:chararray, LoanAccountNumber:chararray,
SanctionedLoanAmount:float, Currency:chararray, DisbusedLoanAmount:float,
LoanStatus:chararray, RiskInPercentage:float, Location:chararray,
ReasonForTakingLoan:chararray);
```

```
c2 = group c1 generate SUBSTRING(LoanAccountNumber,1,3) as LoanAccountNumber,
RiskInPercentage;
```

```
c3 = group c2 by LoanAccountNumber;
```

```
c4 = foreach c3 generate group,AVG(c2.RiskInPercentage);
```

```
dump c4;
```

```
store c4 into '/AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerCategoryAndLoanType';
```

```
(HL,21.92)
(PL,12.041666666666666)
(RL,0.0)
(VL,6.416666666666667)
grunt>
grunt> store c4 into '/AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerCategoryAndLoanType';
```

Figure 17. Result of the third analysis

The fourth analysis solves the problems related to overall average risk per location and category calculation.

```
lc1 = load '/sqoop_out/filteredData.csv' using PigStorage(',') as (CustomerID:int,
Surname:chararray, GivenName:chararray, LoanAccountNumber:chararray,
SanctionedLoanAmount:float, Currency:chararray, DisbusedLoanAmount:float,
LoanStatus:chararray, RiskInPercentage:float, Location:chararray,
ReasonForTakingLoan:chararray);
```

```
lc2 = foreach lc1 generate Location as Location, RiskInPercentage, SUBSTRING(
LoanAccountNumber,1,3) as LoanAccountNumber;
```

```
lc3 = group lc2 by (LoanAccountNumber, Location);
```

```
lc4 = foreach lc3 generate group,AVG(lc2,RiskInPercentage);
```

```
dump lc4;
```

```
store lc4 into '/AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerLocationAndCategory';
```

```
((VL,Koh Kong),6.5)
((VL,Prey Veng),6.5)
((VL,Phnom Penh),6.333333333333333)
((VL,Svay Rieng),6.333333333333333)
grunt> store lc4 into '/AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerLocationAndCategory';
```

Figure 18. Result of the fourth analysis

After completed the analysis, all the output datasets are stored in '/AnalyzedData' directory.

```

root@hadoop:/home/mony# hadoop fs -ls /AnalyzedData
24/08/04 04:48:36 WARN util.NativeCodeLoader: Unable to load native-hadoop library for your platform... usi
va classes where applicable
Found 3 items
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup          0 2024-08-04 04:32 /AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerCategoryAndLoanType
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup          0 2024-08-04 04:21 /AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerLocation
drwxr-xr-x - root supergroup          0 2024-08-04 04:45 /AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerLocationAndCategory

```

Figure 19. Datasets result storing after analysis.

Interpretation of results

The first analysis solves the problems related to overall average risks calculation is 10.216494845360824 of all individual risk.

```

grunt> s3 = foreach s2 gener
grunt> dump s3;
(10.216494845360824)
grunt>

```

Figure 20. Interpretation of the first analysis

The second analysis solves the problems related to overall average risk per location calculation including Kep is 10.166666666666666, Takeo is 10.533333333333333, Kandal is 9.928571428571429, Koh Kong is 10.428571428571429, Prey Veng is 9.428571428571429, Phnom Penh is 10.142857142857142 and Svay Rieng 10.857142857142858.

```

(Kep,10.166666666666666)
(Takeo,10.533333333333333)
(Kandal,9.928571428571429)
(Koh Kong,10.428571428571429)
(Prey Veng,9.428571428571429)
(Phnom Penh,10.142857142857142)
(Svay Rieng,10.857142857142858)

```

Figure 21. Interpretation of the second analysis

The third analysis solves the problems related to overall average risk per category and loan type calculation including HL(Mortgage) 21.92, PL(Small business loan) is 12.041666666666666, RL(Personal loan) 0.0 and VL(Auto loan) 6.416666666666667.

```
(HL,21.92)
(PL,12.041666666666666)
(RL,0.0)
(VL,6.416666666666667)
```

Figure 22. Interpretation of the third analysis

The fourth analysis solves the problems related to overall average risk per location and category calculation including (HL,Kep) is 22.0, (HL,Takeo) is 23.0, (HL,Kandal) is 22.0, (HL,Koh Kong) is 22.0, (HL,Prey Veng) is 21.5, (HL,Phnom Penh) is 21.5, (HL,Svay Rieng) is 21.5, (PL,Kep) is 12.333333333333334, (PL,Takeo) is 11.75, (PL,Kandal) is 11.75, (PL,Koh Kong) is 13.5, (PL,Prey Veng) is 10.0, (PL,Phnom Penh) is 12.333333333333334, (PL,Svay Rieng) is 11.75, (RL,Kep) is 0.0, (RL,Takeo) is 0.0, (RL,Kandal) is 0.0, (RL,Koh Kong) is 0.0, (RL,Prey Veng) is 0.0, (RL,Phnom Penh) is 0.0, (RL,Svay Rieng) is 0.0, (VL,Kep) is 6.333333333333333, (VL,Takeo) is 6.333333333333333, (VL,Kandal) is 6.5, (VL,Koh Kong) is 6.5, (VL,Prey Veng) is 6.5, (VL,Phnom Penh) is 6.333333333333333 and (VL,Svay Rieng) is 6.333333333333333.

```
((HL,Kep),22.0)
((HL,Takeo),23.0)
((HL,Kandal),22.0)
((HL,Koh Kong),22.0)
((HL,Prey Veng),21.5)
((HL,Phnom Penh),21.5)
((HL,Svay Rieng),21.5)
((PL,Kep),12.333333333333334)
((PL,Takeo),11.75)
((PL,Kandal),11.75)
((PL,Koh Kong),13.5)
((PL,Prey Veng),10.0)
((PL,Phnom Penh),12.333333333333334)
((PL,Svay Rieng),11.75)
((RL,Kep),0.0)
((RL,Takeo),0.0)
((RL,Kandal),0.0)
((RL,Koh Kong),0.0)
((RL,Prey Veng),0.0)
((RL,Phnom Penh),0.0)
((RL,Svay Rieng),0.0)
((VL,Kep),6.333333333333333)
((VL,Takeo),6.333333333333333)
((VL,Kandal),6.5)
((VL,Koh Kong),6.5)
((VL,Prey Veng),6.5)
((VL,Phnom Penh),6.333333333333333)
((VL,Svay Rieng),6.333333333333333)
```

Figure 23. Interpretation of the fourth analysis

Quality of insights obtained

From secoda.com, the essential strategies for optimizing data analysis are outcome are: establish clear objectives, ensure data quality, choose appropriate tools, understand the context, utilize visualizations, keep learning and updating skills, collaborate with others, document your process, focus on actionable insights, and communicate effectively (*Best Practices for Data Analysis / SECODA*, n.d.). For this case, the objectives that the owner's company provided very clear with related datasets and they are normalized and cleaned with appropriate tools such as 'sqoop' is used to import data from database and Pig is used to clean and analyze data. For data visualization in the next phase, Power BI will be used by importing data from Hadoop, transforming and cleaning in Power Query Editor and Analyzing and Visualizing in Power BI.

Data Visualization

Selection of appropriate visualizations

Even though Apache Hadoop runs on Ubuntu Linux machine but Microsoft Power BI Desktop can still import via network connection to get dataset from HDFS to visualize on the Windows 10 machine.

Figure 24. Getting data from Hadoop to Power BI

This means Power BI is still one of the best Business Intelligence and Visualization tool that can visual data from Apache Hadoop. To do so, by clicking ‘Get data’ drop down menu in ‘Home’ tab, and click ‘more’. Next is clicking Other and click Hadoop File (HDFS) and clicking Continue button.

Next is filling the Server url and cick OK button. The server url are the combination of Apache Hadoop server’s IP address, HDFS port number and path of directory and file name as below. hdfs://192.168.100.102:54310/AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerCategoryAndLoanType/part-r-00000, then to transform data process is clicking ‘Load’ button.

Figure 25. Importing data from Hadoop by using file system path url

In ‘Power Query Editor’, the dataset can be transformed by changing column names, column data types, and table name. To save these editing is clicking ‘Close & Apply’ button.

For another dataset importing, it just do the same steps except using different server's url. In this case the dataset that need to import are the following server's url.

```
hdfs://192.168.100.102:54310/AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerLocation/part-r-00000
```

```
hdfs://192.168.100.102:54310/AnalyzedData/AverageRiskPerLocationAndCategory/part-r-00000
```

```
hdfs://192.168.100.102:54310/sqoop_out/filteredData.csv/part-m-00000
```

Finally of the importing dataset, The Power BI has four tables such as Customers, AverageRiskPerLocation, AverageRiskPerCategoryAndLoanType and AverageRiskPerLocationAndCategory.

Figure 27. Datasets after tranforming

For visualization tasks, there are four parts are displaying on the ‘Dashboard’.

Figure 28. Visualization PTC Microfinance Plc. Risk Analysis in Power BI

First is displaying the descriptive statistics analysis in six ‘Cards’ including counting of risk transaction is 97, standard deviation of risk is 8.38%, variance of risk is 70.25%, minimum of risk is 0%, average of risk is 10.22% and maximum of risk is 26%. Second is a left table displaying the average risk per location and category by showing three columns such as loan type, location and sum of value. Third is a pie chart that displaying the average risk per category and loan type such as HL is 54.29%, PL is 29.82%, VL is 15.89% and RL is 0%. The last is stacked column chart that are displaying the average risk per location including Svay Rieng is 10.9%, Takeo is 10.5%, Koh Kong is 10.4%, Kep is 10.2%, Phnom Penh is 10.1%, Kandal is 9.9% and Prey Veng is 9.4%.

Effective communication of insights and best practices in data visualization

The aim of data visualization is to simplify complex and large dataset or information to make them easy to follow and understand. The best of five effective communication of insight practices such as understand the audience, choose the right visualization tool, clear the clutter,

use less fonts, and use colors creatively (Quach & Quach, 2024). Understanding the audience is essential at the first step, stakeholder's purpose, dataset, and business problem are need to solved by data analytics and visualizations. Power BI plays as important role of visualization tools that used to visualize data in many categories are bar chart, pie chart, scatter plot, and so on. All visualization charts and graphs on the dashboard must be simple, clean, and short paragraph but meaningful. Using a few font names and color are the best way to attract the attention of the audiences. In Figure 28 on the dashboard used only black and dark blue color on the white background. This styles make the texts and numbers look very clear to view and read. Appreciating and carefully considering the technical components of data presentation is necessary for good data visualization. However, there is also a creative component to it. Decisions are based on the story that wish to tell, and design choices are motivated by the desire to present that story to our audience as effectively as possible. Use default settings for most graphical elements in software systems (Best Practices for Data Visualisation, n.d.).

Conclusion

Big Data Technologies and Analytics is one of the most important parts in information technology or data science field. Its theory and practical can be applied in technological fields such as big data analysis and visualization. Apache Hadoop, Apache Spark, Apache Pig, Power BI and so on are the core concepts that come from big data technology plays as an important role to help many people success in their careers as Data engineer.

Especially, big data technologies and analytics is used other fields include business, education, government or sport. Even though new technology grows rapidly, it is still playing as an important role and still used along to it.

References

- Apache Hadoop: What is it and how can you use it?* (n.d.). Databricks.
<https://www.databricks.com/glossary/hadoop>
- BasuMallick, C. (2022, August 8). *What is big data? Definition and best practices - Spiceworks Inc.* Spiceworks Inc. <https://www.spiceworks.com/tech/big-data/articles/what-is-big-data/>
- Best Practices for Data Analysis | SECODA.* (n.d.). <https://www.secodaco.co/learn/best-practices-for-data-analysis>
- Best practices for data visualisation.* (n.d.). Best Practices for Data Visualisation. <https://royal-statistical-society.github.io/datavisguide/>
- GeeksforGeeks. (2021, August 19). *Overview of SQOOP in Hadoop.* GeeksforGeeks.
<https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/overview-of-sqoop-in-hadoop/>
- How Sqoop internally works.* (2018, January 13). <https://community.cloudera.com/t5/Support-Questions/How-Sqoop-internally-works/m-p/108018/highlight/true>
- Quach, S., & Quach, S. (2024, April 11). *Leverage Data Visualization for effective communication.* Knowi. <https://www.knowi.com/blog/data-visualization-for-effective-communication/>
- Ranadive, P. (2024, June 13). *HDFS Tutorial: Architecture, Read & Write Operation using Java API.* Guru99. <https://www.guru99.com/learn-hdfs-a-beginners-guide.html>
- Staff, C. (2024, April 1). *What is big data analytics? definition, benefits, and more.* Coursera.
<https://www.coursera.org/articles/big-data-analytics>
- What is Hadoop: Architecture, Modules, Advantages, History - javatpoint.* (n.d.).
www.javatpoint.com. <https://www.javatpoint.com/what-is-hadoop>
- What is the purpose of the JPS command in Hadoop ? | ResearchGate.* (n.d.). ResearchGate.
https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_is_the_purpose_of_the_JPS_command_in_Hadoop

ITDS520 - Assignment Rubric

Student's Full Name: MONY HO

EIU ID: EIU95527

Category	Marks Allocation	Marks Attained	Comments
1. Data Ingestion and Pre-processing	15 marks	13	
2. Big Data Technologies	20 marks	15	
3. Data Analytics	35 marks	28	
4. Data Visualization	15 marks	12	
5. Report and Presentation	15 marks	12	
<p>*** Penalty *** This penalty is for papers that do not meet the assignment requirements. (i.e. word count, format, etc.)</p>	(-5)		
Total marks allocated and achieved:	100 marks	80	